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The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase

HORIZON 2020 PROJECT

ALL-Ready in a nutshell

Agroecology is a different way of farming and organising food systems. It is a way of working with food that uses diversity, considers the local context, and employs adaptive management at all levels of the agri-food system. Agroecology is not just a concern of producers. It is rather a profound change in reasoning about the shape and role of food systems, and so includes citizens and policy makers at the local and global level, individually and collectively. To set up the framework and pave the way for a future network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition, the ALL-Ready consortium identified the key principles, concepts, and criteria which are applicable to place-based open innovation arrangements such as living labs (LLs) and research infrastructures (RIs).

7 main outcomes to produce

A Mission and Vision document for the Network (validated by the wider community) specifying how it can contribute to EU objectives and policy goals

A wide-scale mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms (for participatory agroecological research and innovation for the Network implementation)

A pilot Network of LLs and RIs to test the functioning and activities of the Network

An implementation plan for the Network

Recommendations to ensure the long term implementation and sustainability of the Network

A capacity building programme including training actions and packages

Evidence-based knowledge to support the transition to Agroecology

The ALL-Ready pilot network

The pilot network will help to build strong links and cooperation between the different agroecology-focused living labs, research infrastructures and open innovation arrangements across Europe. It currently brings together 15 initiatives from all over Europe. The network will prepare joint activities in line with the common agroecological interest of the pilot members: i) knowledge exchange, ii) collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials (e.g. sustainable soil management, diversification), iii) long-term monitoring of agroecosystems, iv) short food supply chain practices etc.. Furthermore the pilot network is also used to test and validate the concepts and tools developed in the project regarding the inclusion criteria and governance of the future European network of living labs and research infrastructures.

STAKEHOLDERS

- Funding bodies
- Extension services
- Citizens & consumers
- Networks
- Farmers & farmer associations
- Scientists
- Education bodies
- Policy makers

PILOT NETWORK

- Research Infrastructure
- Living Lab
- Both

Paving the way to the agroecology transition in Europe

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